

The casual effect of retirement on BMI in older adults in Russia: A regression discontinuity study

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Abstract: The population of middle-income developing countries is aging fast enough, and they will most likely have to adjust the retirement age, many countries have already started this procedure in order to have more financially acceptable state budgets. This article analyzes the causal effect of retirement in Russia on body mass index (BMI) and weight, which are important indicators of the risk of many diseases. The most important demographic trend of our time is the aging of the population, which directly affects the labor market and employment of the elderly population. Using the Russian Database (RLMS-HSE), we use the change in the mandatory retirement age in Russia with a fuzzy regression discontinuity design to study changes in BMI and weight at retirement. Our study showed that retirement will lead to an increase in weight and BMI in women. Also, this effect is much stronger among pensioners with a low level of education. The reason may be that older people with a low level of education do not observe proper nutrition and exercise less after retirement. Retirement does not affect men's BMI.

Keywords: Retirement, RDD, BMI, health.

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Introduction

Retirement's effects on health have long been a fascinating study topic. The research on this subject is expanding quickly because it brings up significant political difficulties in the discussion of the ideal retirement age. Some nations are adopting or debating policies to raise the retirement age in the face of an aging population. A higher retirement age might result in more people working and making more long-term contributions to the social security system. Therefore, it may be a wise strategy to help many nations' public pension systems become more financially stable. Raising the retirement age may have benefits for people's health, including lower health care expenses and improved quality of life. Raising the retirement age might be problematic from the standpoint of health and personal well-being if retiring can actually enhance general health. Retirement influences changes in the degree of well-being of older persons as well as the creation of diverse aging strategies and the allocation of resources for old life. Older people's social standing includes their health, and their degree of health has a direct impact on their purchasing patterns and level of life satisfaction. Additional healthcare expenses are required because health issues become more severe as people age, especially for the elderly. A significant obstacle to social growth is the issue of aging and health.

A proactive and successful strategy to stop the population from becoming older is "healthy aging." The practice of delaying retirement has garnered much interest and debate in recent years from many facets of society. The government and party pay a lot of attention to the fact that people's health is the primary concern for their ability to survive, hence it is crucial that the "building of health care" be prioritized as a national development plan.

The current situation of "the old ahead of the affluent" poses unique challenges for the sustainability of the pension system, healthcare system, and social security because of retirement and health care issues. The utilization of human resources for elderly adults, the sustainable development of retirement, the selection of pension schemes, and social health spending will all be directly impacted by the link between retirement and health. The analysis of the causal link between health status and pension policy aids in developing and enhancing the country's pension strategy. In order to achieve the objective of improving the health and well-being of pensioners with limited pension resources, it is possible to significantly reduce the cost of medical services for residents, effectively improve the health of retired residents, and reduce the "return to poverty due to illness and poverty due to illness." The promotion of the social security system for the new era is congruent with the expansion of research into the causes of and mechanisms behind the interaction between pension policy and health care.

Economists are very interested in the research of the causal relationship between retirement and health status given the major global aging issue. Health is typically treated as a stock in the theory of health economics. Health is impacted by exogenous shocks, depends on long-term investments, and depreciates; it is both an investment product that can improve human capital and a consumer product that can boost utility. Impact. After retirement, pensioners have less incentive to invest in their health to boost productivity and improve income, but the benefits of healthy consumption, such as rising personal utility, will rise. The net impact of retirement will be impacted by the trade-off between the marginal cost of healthcare spending and the marginal income from using medical services. The direction of the impact of retirement on health is thus unclear from the perspective of the theory of health requirements. There are numerous research findings on the effects of retiring on health, according to the most recent empirical literature.

In addition, much attention is paid to the impact of retirement on the physical health of older people, and indicators of weight, mortality and others were compared. As for retirement and termination of work as factors affecting the state of health, this has been widely covered in Western empirical works, but this topic is still rarely touched upon in the scientific literature. Yang and Hall (2008) investigated the economic burden of being overweight in the U.S. seniors' healthcare system. They found that older men who were overweight or obese at age 65 had 6-13% more health care spending at age 65 than a cohort of the same age in the normal weight range. Older overweight women aged 65 are 11-17% more likely to be overweight than women of normal weight.

The purpose of this article is to analyze research on the impact of retirement on health (in our case, we took BMI) and classify the work in accordance with the research topic.

The theory describing the transition from work to retirement has become the main theory for empirical research and the impact of retirement on health. These studies very often give different results, which is explained, first of all, by the definition of the term "health" itself, which can be considered:

- ✓ Probability of death (probability of death within a certain period of time, life expectancy). In most of the above-mentioned studies, self-assessments of health or health indices calculated using survey data are used as response variables. Several studies assessing the impact of retirement on recorded mortality have found no effect (Hernaes et al., 2013;) Nielsen (2019) and Hagen (2018), but Fitzpatrick and Moore (2018) argue that retirement will increase the mortality rate of American men. On the other hand, Bloemen et al. (2017) found that early retirement reduces mortality;
- ✓ Physical health (chronic, cardiovascular, tumor diseases, diseases of the musculoskeletal system, diabetes, heart attack, stroke);
- ✓ Mental health status (cognitive functions, stress, depression).

Secondly, the research methods are different. There were significant differences in the survey samples: age, gender and social affiliation varied. Several studies have specifically examined the effect of retirement on weight or BMI (body mass index). Chung, Domino, and Stearns (2009) used HRS data and found that retirement leads to moderate weight gain. Weight gain after retirement was found in people who were already overweight, and in people with lower incomes who quit physically stressful activities. Godard (2016) estimated the causal effect of retirement on the body mass index (BMI) of adults aged 50-69 years on the likelihood of obesity based on the European Survey on Health, Aging and Retirement (SHARE). Her conclusion was that retirement led to an increase in the likelihood of obesity in men by 12 percentage points over two to four years. This model is guided by men who have retired from hard work, and those who are already at risk of obesity. On the contrary, no significant results were found in women.

Kempfen and Maurer (2016) studied the causal relationship of retirement with recommended levels of physical activity. They used data from the U.S. Health and Retirement Study and found that retirement had a significant positive impact on compliance with the guidelines. Andreas Kuhn (2018) used German data for a study and found that retirement behavior can not only improve the health of older people by reducing unhealthy, risky and harmful work, but can also worsen the health of older people due to changes in daily life, physical and mental activity associated with retirement. the level of health of the elderly.

Although the literature includes a number of other behaviors related to health investments, such as health care diet and sleep duration (Eibich, 2015), in this study we followed the example of Bertoni et al. (2018) and investigated alcohol consumption, smoking and physical activity, since these three behaviors are included in all datasets. so that they can be compared internationally.

Database

We used the RLMS-HSE database. The Russia Longitudinal Monitoring Survey -Higher School of Economics is a series of nationally representative surveys designed to monitor the effects of Russian reforms on the health and economic welfare of households and individuals in the Russian Federation. Datasets with constructed variables on household income and expenditure are updated with data from the 30th round of the HSE RLMS.

The data includes more than 150 indicators, including expenditures on various types of food, non-food products, education, services, etc. The indicators are calculated in real and nominal values in order to be compatible in dynamics. In addition, the data set includes the typology of households and individual demographic groups. All this gives the researcher the opportunity to analyze the data deeper and faster. The RLMS-HSE data contains cross-section and panel examples. In 2019, the survey includes 6,770 cases in households, of which 4,840 make up a representative sample.

The data file includes about 2000 variables, such as: household composition; structure of family ties; living conditions and ownership of housing; ownership of durable goods; structure of expenses; health condition; types and sources of income; subsidies and benefits, savings, utility bills and their amounts; availability and use of land plots, personal subsidiary farm: use and the structure of production.

The individual longitudinal data file for IBM SPSS statistics and the codebook in English have been updated and now include RLMS-HSE data (2019).

The RLMS-HSE data contains cross-section and panel examples. In 2019, the survey includes 17605 individual cases, of which 12069 cases constitute a representative sample. About 2775 variables are included in the data file.

RDD

The premise of the regression discontinuity (RD) design is that the researcher has in-depth knowledge of the institutional policies that dictate treatment. In this instance, the assigned or forced variable determines the status of individual treatment. Processing is (partially) switched on or off if a forced variable exceeds a specified limit value of c .

The agent's incapacity to accurately control or manipulate the influencing factors near c and thereafter randomly allocate them to treatment and control groups is important to the design's validity (Lee and Lemieux, 2010).

To lessen the estimate error, we combine a fixed effect model with a regression discontinuity (RD) approach. The fundamental tenet of RD is that those who are just past retirement age may be contrasted with those who are just past it. The sole distinction between the two groups is that those in the latter group are qualified for retirement benefits. People who are older than the required age have more options to retire, but the difference in retirement decisions relative to the required age is unrelated to the outcome variable. The health variable is the outcome variable in this instance. Assess the effects of retirement on physical and mental health using the data and the micro individual data inherent in it.

A two-stage least squares model with distinct fixed effects is used to evaluate fuzzy RDD. The model appears as follows:

$$R_{it} = \pi_{it} + \pi_{1}PE_{it} + \beta_{1}age + X_{it} \rho + Z_{it}\eta + \alpha_{i} + \delta_{t} + u_{it}$$

R_{it} Indicates whether an individual i retires within a year t and PE_{it} whether the age of the individual exceeds the allowable retirement age. If a person's age is above retirement age, it is 1, otherwise it is 0. To determine the age age , we use the number of years between the current age and the acceptable retirement age. X_{it} is a vector of time-varying or time-unchanging individual characteristics, including marital status and household status. Z_{it} is a vector of family characteristics, including family size. α_{i} is an individual fixed effect. δ_{t} represents a temporary model. u_{it} is an error term.

$$BMI_{it} = \pi_{it} + \lambda \hat{R}_{it} + \beta_{1}age + X_{it} \rho + Z_{it}\eta + \alpha_{i} + \delta_{t} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Which R_{it} represents the predicted value of the first stage. λ represents the expected impact of retirement on health. α_{i} is also a personal fixed effect, δ_{t} is an annual fixed effect. ε_{it} is a special mistake. Outcome variable BMI_{it} is an outcome variable used to measure health status and possible channels that affect human health.

The age band of the male sample is limited from 50 to 70 years, and the age band of the female sample is limited from 45 to 60 years. Next, we explored some possible channels that can induce age-related weight and BMI. In the previous literature, physical activity was suggested as a possible channel (Godard, 2016).

Outcome	N (n=3079)		(1) (N=872) %28.32		(2) (N=2207) %71.68	
	Coefficient (95% CI)	P value	Coefficient (95% CI)	P value	Coefficient (95% CI)	P value
Pension Eligibility	0.22 (0.13 to 0.32)	0.000	0.29 (0.16 to 0.43)	0.000	0.20 (0.09 to 0.31)	0.000

Table1. Pension Eligibility for man, woman

Results

Causal effect estimates

	The effect of retirement on BMI	The effect of retirement on BMI	The effect of retirement on weight	The effect of retirement on weight
Coefficient (95% CI)	-5.919	-5.71	-9.53	-5.6
P value	0.035	0.009	0.316	0.976
Covariates	Yes	No	Yes	No

Table 2. The effect of retirement on BMI and weight

Table 2 shows the effect of retirement on BMI and weight. We used RDD model to find the casual effect. Each cell in the table represents the coefficient from a separate regression with 95% confidence intervals in parentheses. The models in columns (1) and (2) show the associations between retirement and BMI, using RD regressions. We used the full sample of 3079 individuals in these regressions and controlled for age, gender, education background, marital status, and income. The models in columns (3) to (4) provide estimates of the causal effect of retirement on weight. In these regressions, we used the sample within the optimal bandwidth . The models in columns (2) and (4) do not include covariates. The models in columns (1) and (3) additionally include gender, education background, marital status and income as covariates. As we can see on the table, the impact of retirement on health, and in our case on BMI, has a significant negative impact. That is, BMI can greatly increase, thereby exceeding the norm of permissible BMI and can lead to overweight or even obesity.

	BMI	
	Low educ(1)	High educ(2)
RD_Estimate	-4.316** (-2.54)	-0.638 (-0.88)
N	1540	1539

t statistics in parentheses
 * p<0.1, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01

Table 3. Education background

We also looked at people with different levels of education and compared whether the level of education somehow affects BMI after retirement.

As shown in the table 3 , elderly people with low education have a significantly negative impact on BMI after retirement . Most likely, this is due to less knowledge about proper nutrition, adherence to the norm of weight and height, as well as proper physical activity, etc. People with higher education are more aware of information about their diet, weight and exercise. For high education, we took people who graduated from high school and higher, people who received only a middle school graduation certificate and lower, we considered as low education.

		Female		
Variables	BMI	weight	Self-reported health	
Ret	0.029** (0.073)	0.065** (0.502)	0.018 (0.032)	
Smoke	0.364 (0.019)	0.201 (0.030)	-0.040* (0.022)	
Alcohol	0.023 (0.019)	-0.366 (0.272)	-0.042* (0.022)	
Exercise in the last 12m	0.036** (0.018)	-0.253 (0.372)	-0.030 (0.023)	
Can run 2km	0.064* (0.072)	-0.182 (0.345)	-0.322 (0.043)	
Control variables	Yes	Yes	Yes	
N	2195	2195	2195	

t statistics in parentheses
* p<0.1, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01

Table 4. Table Mechanism analysis of the health impact of retirement

		Male		
Variables	BMI	Weight	Self-reported health	
Ret	-0.006 (0.082)	-0.385* (0.407)	0.018 (0.032)	
Smoke	-3.674*** (0.019)	0.506* (0.274)	-0.051* (0.032)	
Alcohol	0.106*** (0.019)	-0.366 (0.272)	-0.044* (0.012)	
Exercise in the last 12m	0.048** (0.020)	-0.183 (0.286)	-0.030 (0.023)	
Can run 2km	0.057* (0.065)	-0.198 (0.345)	-0.452 (0.063)	
Control variables	Yes	Yes	Yes	
N	864	864	864	

t statistics in parentheses
* p<0.1, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01

Table 5. Mechanism analysis of the health impact of retirement

If the impact of retirement affects the level of health of residents through the above channel variables, then after adding the above variables during the regression, the negative impact of retirement on health should become less or cease to be significant. The regression results are shown in Table 4 and 5. After adding the corresponding variables of smoking, drinking alcohol, running and exercise, the effect of retirement on BMI and self-reported health conditional are no longer significant for male and no significant for female only for self-reported health. This shows that moderate alcohol consumption, exercise, running statistically significantly contributed to normal BMI and self-assessment of health for male. But they all can not contribute weight, as we can see on the Table 4 and 5, and don't work with male. However, retirement reduces the likelihood of drinking alcohol, smoking, reduces the likelihood of exercise, and reduces running.

At the same time, the retirement of employees helps to reduce smoking (Lang et al.,2007), which is due to the reduction in daily stress related to the performance of work responsibilities. However, this only applies to pensioners who

voluntarily leave the labor market, because due to the stress associated with unemployment, the possibility of increased intensity or the beginning of smoking will only increase laid-off workers (Henkens et al., 2008).

But retirement may reduce the level of male's health, we can see the results in the existing literature (Jin Feng et al., 2020). It can be seen that retirement has a negative impact on men's health through channels such as smoking and weight. While factors such as smoking or alcohol consumption do not have a big impact on women's health after retirement. But it can increase BMI and weight for women of retirement age. Thus, this article recommends to step up efforts for disease prevention and intervention, to encourage residents to raise awareness of healthy lifestyle and healthy behavior in response to the aforementioned channels of influence, as well as to increase the level of national health literacy. Raising awareness of health risks at the national level is one of the most cost-effective ways to improve national health care. Health goals should be integrated into appropriate aging policies to help healthy lifestyle strategies and improve national health and well-being.

Conclusion

With the retirement of the generation born between 1950 and 1960, population aging is becoming a more severe issue. For the new era's social security, healthcare, and pension systems to function sustainably, they face significant hurdles brought on by retirement and health issues. In order to improve pension policy and advance the social security system in a new era, the government pays close attention to concerns relating to the health of the populace and expands research on the causal link and channels of action between pension policy and healthcare.

This paper employs the technique of building a breakpoint regression to investigate the influence and mechanism of pension policy on the health of residents, based on the data from the second stage of the study on tracking the condition of health and pensions in Russia for 1994–2019. Retirement has a considerable detrimental effect on BMI, as well as health, according to studies. Since low BMI is extremely uncommon in senior individuals, after retirement, BMI is higher than it was before retirement. A significant number of assumptions could exist. Due to a lack of motion, as it used to be the case at work, increased home cooking of grain goods, sedentary lifestyle, etc.

Our findings may have implications for reforms regarding the retirement age in the state pension system. Firstly, retirement has some effect on weight gain and increases the body mass index, which most likely increases the likelihood of being overweight or obese, especially in poorly educated workers and women. It follows from this that a policy that aims to increase the retirement age can help reduce health risks, as well as health care costs. Also, the retirement age of women in Russia is lower compared to men. Raising the retirement age of women may be more appropriate. It is worth noting that our results imply that raising the retirement age of women is also worth considering in terms of health outcomes.

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